

Year: 2026

CASE STUDY:

The Impact of Inclusive Education on Teachers and Peers: A Case Study from an EYFS Classroom

1. Introduction

Inclusive education is now a central part of early years practice, and in principle it promotes fairness and equal access for all children. In reality, however, it brings very practical classroom challenges that affect teachers and other children in daily learning situations.

This case study is based on my own classroom experience as an EYFS teacher, and reflects what I observed over time while working with a mixed-ability group of young children.

2. Classroom Context

The classroom consisted of 18 children aged between 2.8 and 4 years. We followed an inclusive approach where all children participated in the same learning environment, with adjustments made where needed.

One child in particular, aged 2.8 years, had a diagnosis of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). The child had previously received therapeutic support, but in the classroom setting continued to show high levels of activity, impulsivity, and difficulty with group routines.

3. What I Observed in Practice

Very early on, I noticed that transitions and group times were the most challenging parts of the day.

For example, during circle time, the child would often leave the carpet without warning or move around the room, which would sometimes distract other children. In free play, there were moments where toys were taken suddenly from peers, and this occasionally led to pushing or hitting when other children reacted.

One situation I remember clearly happened during a table activity just before lunch. A child was using counting blocks, and the child quickly took them, which led to a short conflict. I had to step in immediately to calm both children and restore the activity.

What made this difficult was not just the behaviour itself, but the fact that the rest of the class still needed attention and learning time at the same moment.

Prepared by:

M.Ed (2018), B.Ed (2016)

MSC (Hons) Agriculture Economics

EYFS FS1/FS2 Class Teacher

Dubai, UAE

adaa80@yahoo.com

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4. Thinking About Why This Was Happening

Over time, I began to understand these behaviours as part of difficulties with self-regulation rather than intentional disruption.

From what I know about ADHD, children often struggle with impulse control and waiting for turns, which explained many of the incidents I was seeing.

I also noticed that other children in the class were affected by what they observed. In some moments, a few children began reacting loudly or emotionally during conflict situations, which showed how strongly they were picking up on peer behaviour.

5. What I Did in the Classroom

In response, I tried a number of strategies gradually rather than all at once:

I introduced a more predictable routine, because I noticed the child responded slightly better when the structure of the day was consistent. I also started using very immediate praise when positive behaviour appeared, even in small moments like waiting or sharing.

Tasks were broken into shorter parts, because longer activities were not manageable for sustained attention. At times, I had to gently remove the child from a situation and redirect them before the behaviour escalated further.

I also stayed in regular contact with parents so that expectations at home and school were more aligned.

6. What Changed and What Didn't

There were small improvements over time. The child began to settle slightly better during familiar routines, especially when support was consistent. There were also moments of positive interaction with peers during structured activities.

However, unstructured times like free play and transitions remained difficult. These were the moments where most incidents still happened.

For the rest of the class, I noticed something important as well. Some children became slightly hesitant during group play after disruptions, and I also felt that I was not always able to give equal attention to everyone at the same time.

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adaa80@yahoo.com

7. Reflection on My Experience

This experience made me reflect quite deeply on what inclusion looks like in real classroom conditions.

While I fully support the idea of inclusive education, I also realised that implementing it well depends heavily on available support. There were moments where I felt stretched between managing one child's immediate needs and supporting the rest of the class.

I also realised that I was still developing my own classroom strategies for handling such situations, and much of my learning came through day-to-day experience rather than formal training alone.

At times, I genuinely felt that additional support in the classroom would have changed the experience significantly for everyone involved.

8. Conclusion and Recommendations

This case shows that inclusive education is both valuable and complex in practice. It supports the idea of shared learning, but it also creates real challenges when classroom support is limited.

From this experience, I would suggest:

- more in-class support such as teaching assistants or shadow support
- smaller group ratios in early years inclusive classrooms
- more practical training for teachers on behavioural support strategies
- stronger collaboration between school and parents
- attention to teacher wellbeing in inclusive settings

9. Brief Link to Research

My experience reflects wider research which suggests that inclusion works best when there is sufficient support in place. Without this, both teacher workload and peer learning can be affected, even when the intention of inclusion is positive.

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